

Virtual Reality based serious games for memory skill improvement

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Abstract: In our laboratory, we are dedicated to harnessing Virtual Reality (VR) for the enhancement and assessment of memory, with a primary focus on older adults coping with Alzheimer's, dementia, or those looking to improve their memory. We employ the Oculus Quest 2 VR device operating on Android 10 in conjunction with the Unity game engine to develop these applications. Our memory games assess spatial, episodic, and auditory memory using tests such as the Corsi Block-Tapping Test, memorization tasks, and auditory challenges. These games include modified versions of classics like "Simon," memory card games, and even a shopping simulation.

Introduction

We are developing serious VR-based games designed to involve patients in memory enhancement programs. These games are tailored for older adults coping with conditions such as Alzheimer's, dementia, or those seeking memory improvement. The interactive nature of VR fosters sustained engagement and encourages patients to actively partake in their therapy. This approach not only benefits individual patients but also alleviates the strain on healthcare facilities and caregivers while promoting patient independence and self-esteem. [1-5]

Materials and Methods

In our lab, we focus on developing virtual reality (VR)-based serious games that have proven effective for rehabilitation. We leverage the powerful Oculus Quest 2, a VR device operating on Android 10, known for its seamless performance and user-friendly interface. This technology provides high-resolution displays and advanced tracking capabilities, immersing users in our carefully crafted virtual worlds. Complementing the Oculus Quest 2, our VR experiences feature Oculus Touch controllers,

meticulously designed for intuitive interaction. These controllers boast an analog joystick, three function buttons, a grip button, and a trigger button, all positioned for maximum control and responsiveness. They're equipped with advanced sensors like accelerometers, gyroscopes, and haptic motors, ensuring precise tracking of users' hand movements. Infrared LEDs in the controllers' rings enhance their 3D tracking capabilities, delivering a truly immersive experience and promoting effective rehabilitation.[6]

Figure 1. Oculus Quest 2 virtual device [6].

For the software development aspect of our serious games, we rely on the powerful Unity game engine. Unity has emerged as a leading platform for creating immersive and interactive experiences in the world of VR. Its versatility and user-friendly interface empower our team to design captivating virtual environments and engaging gameplay, tailored to the specific needs and preferences of our users. [7]

In addition to engaging gameplay, we place a strong emphasis on the visual aesthetics of our serious games. To bring our virtual worlds to life with stunning graphics and animations, we utilize the Blender 3D computer graphics program. Widely renowned for its capabilities in generating animated films, visual effects, 3D models, and virtual reality content, Blender is an invaluable asset in crafting lifelike and visually captivating environments. [8]

Our mission is to use cutting-edge technology and creativity to develop engaging serious games tailored to patients' rehabilitation needs. We aim to create entertaining and effective experiences, leveraging the power of virtual reality to motivate patients, speed up their progress, and enhance their physical and cognitive well-being.[9-10]

Memory testing with virtual reality devices

We have devoted extensive efforts to the development of memory assessment tools, specifically designed to measure various aspects of memory in an engaging and comprehensive manner. Our dedication to

advancing memory evaluation has led us to create three distinct types of tests, each targeting different memory domains, and providing valuable insights into cognitive capabilities.

The first of these tests is the Corsi Block-Tapping Test, a renowned and widely used evaluation tool for assessing spatial memory. Spatial memory is a fundamental aspect of memory that enables us to remember and recall the location of objects or events in our environment. During the Corsi Block-Tapping Test, participants are presented with a sequence of blocks, which are tapped by the examiner in a specific order. The participant's task is to reproduce the sequence of taps in the same order. By accurately replicating the pattern, individuals demonstrate their ability to retain and reproduce spatial information effectively. [11]

Figure 2. Girl and boy room model in the Corsi test.

Figure 3. Screenshot during the Corsi-test.

The second memory assessment test we have developed involves a memorization test, integrated within a shopping simulation. This test is designed to measure episodic memory, which refers to our ability to recall specific events, experiences, or personal memories. In this simulation,

participants engage in a virtual shopping scenario, where they are presented with a variety of items to select and purchase. After completing the shopping experience, participants are asked to recall the items they purchased, their prices, and other contextual details related to the shopping trip. This test not only evaluates episodic memory but also showcases the integration of memory assessment within real-life scenarios, making the evaluation process more relatable and enjoyable for the participants.

The third memory assessment test focuses on auditory memory, a critical aspect of memory responsible for our ability to retain and reproduce information that we hear. In this test, participants are exposed to a series of auditory stimuli, such as words or phrases (e.g., apple, ball, red). Following the presentation of the stimuli, there is a certain time delay, during which participants engage in unrelated activities. After the delay, participants are then asked to recall as many words or phrases as possible from the initial auditory presentation. By measuring the accuracy and quantity of the recalled auditory information, we gain valuable insights into the individual's auditory memory capacity.

Our memory assessment tests are carefully curated to be user-friendly, engaging, and suitable for a wide range of participants, including older adults and individuals with cognitive impairments. We understand the significance of comprehensive memory evaluation in various contexts, such as cognitive rehabilitation, early detection of memory-related disorders, and monitoring memory changes over time. By utilizing virtual reality technology, we offer a novel and immersive approach to memory assessment, striving to make the evaluation process more enjoyable, accurate, and informative for both participants and healthcare professionals. Through our continuous efforts in memory research and test development, we aim to contribute to the field of cognitive neuroscience and clinical psychology. Our vision is to empower individuals with a deeper understanding of their memory capabilities, foster early interventions for memory-related concerns, and pave the way for future advancements in memory assessment and cognitive enhancement.

Virtual Reality based games to improve memory

At the virtual reality innovation, our team has created three memory games that hold the potential to revolutionize memory training and cognitive enhancement. Each game is thoughtfully designed to target specific aspects of memory, providing users with an engaging and effective means to sharpen their mental acuity.

The first memory game in our repertoire is the captivating "Simon" game, a classic and widely recognized memory training activity. With a focus on improving short-term memory, the Simon game presents users with a visually stimulating interface featuring four colored objects, each emitting a distinct sound when pressed. In a round of the game, the virtual device will illuminate one or more buttons in a random order, creating a sequence of colors and sounds. The challenge lies in the player's ability to reproduce the exact sequence by pressing the buttons in the same order. As users progress through the levels, the complexity and length of the sequences increase, providing a stimulating and rewarding experience that bolsters short-term memory capacity. [12-13]

The second memory game we offer is the timeless classic memory card game, be-loved by generations and now elevated to a whole new level of immersion through virtual reality. Participants are presented with a grid of face-down cards, and their objective is to turn over two cards at a time to find matching pairs. The twist lies in the challenge of remembering the positions of previously revealed cards, as players must rely on their memory to uncover matching pairs efficiently. As the game progresses, the number of cards and difficulty levels escalate, offering a delightful and nostalgic experience while honing spatial memory and recall abilities.

Figure 4. Screenshot during the shopping stimulation game.

Lastly, our team introduces an innovative and engaging shopping simulation as the third memory game. This simulation is designed to stimulate various memory domains, including episodic memory and contextual recall. Participants are virtually transported to a bustling shopping environment, where they navigate through aisles filled with diverse items. Their task is to select specific items based on a given shopping list within a time limit. The shopping list varies in complexity across different levels, necessitating enhanced episodic memory skills as users strive to remember the required items while navigating through the virtual store. This simulation seamlessly integrates memory training into a real-life scenario, enhancing the applicability and relatability of the memory game experience.

Conclusions

Our labor creating virtual reality-based serious games. We utilize the Oculus Quest 2 virtual device. The Unity game engine is leveraged to develop our software. We focus on memory-testing tools and memory-enhancing games. Memory assessment tests cover spatial, episodic, and auditory memory. Memory games include "Simon," a card-matching game, and a shopping simulation.

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